

TESSE²B
the smart energy storage

Thermal Energy Storage Systems for Energy Efficient Buildings

Spain Open Day

TESSe2b technology was officially inaugurated in Spain, on February 9th, in Calonge de Segarra, Barcelona.

The event was attended by several people, including the President of Diputació de Barcelona and the mayor of Calonge de Segarra.

The visit was conducted by members of the project, who explained how **TESSe2b** technology stores solar and geothermal energy in an innovative way.

Learn more about TESSE2b!

The 6th TESSE2b workshop and B2B meeting took place at Graz, Austria, at 10 April 2019.

[Stay tuned for more updates!](#)

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Residential Building Energy Storage by Solar and Geothermal Resources

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